

DELAMINATION BUCKLING AND GROWTH OF COMPOSITE LAMINATED PLATES WITH TRANSVERSE SHEAR DEFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

An analytical method is presented to determine the delamination buckling load and growth of an axially loaded laminated beam-plate with through-the-width delamination at an arbitrary location in loading direction. The influence of the delamination size, depth, and location on initial buckling and strain energy release rate is investigated with consideration of the transverse shear deformation. Results of the analysis show that the delamination buckling load depends on the delamination location, length, and depth. The buckling load is significantly affected by the location of the unsymmetric delamination in axial direction for the relatively thick delamination. Investigated are the effects of the transverse shear deformation on the growth of delamination. The energy release rate with the transverse shear deformation is higher than that without the transverse shear deformation.

Keywords : Delamination buckling, Unsymmetric delamination in loading direction, Delamination growth, Energy release rate, Shear deformation

1. INTRODUCTION

The delaminations due to initial imperfections or in-service damages may reduce the stiffness of the structures and lower the buckling load. It accelerates the ultimate failure of the structures. Therefore a great number of studies have been conducted on this subject.

For the prediction of the ultimate load of the structure with delaminations, the delamination growth as one of the postbuckling characteristics must be considered. There are two approaches that determine the delamination growth. One approach is to use the relation between the interlaminar shear strength of the material and the interlaminar shear stress at the delamination front. The other proposes that growth occurs whenever the strain energy release rate at the delamination front is greater than the fracture toughness of the material. For the first time, Chai [1] analyzed this phenomenon by the Euler column theory and the Griffith's fracture criterion. Yin [2] proposed the energy release rate formulation through J-integral, and Simitses [3] and Yin [4] used this formulation and the Euler column theory for the analysis. Then, since transverse shear modulus in composite laminated structures is much lower than inplane Young's modulus, the effect of transverse shear stress is greatly significant. Recently Kardomateas [5] and Chen [6], *et al.* used shear deformation theory to analyze delamination buckling and growth phenomena.

In this study, the beam-plate is assumed homogeneous and orthotropic. The embedded delamination is located arbitrarily in the beam-plate. The variational principle is applied to calculate the buckling load. The J-integral including shear stress is presented to calculate the strain energy release rate. Investigated are the effects of geometric parameters and the shear deformation on the buckling load and the energy release rate.

2. ANALYTIC PROCEDURE

2.1. Governing Equations

The geometry is shown in Figure 1 for the considered beam-plate of length L and thickness H . The delaminated layer of length a , thickness h , is located parallel to the reference plane. The buckling of the beam-plate is one dimensional problem that there is no curvature in the width direction. These geometric characteristics do not change during the buckling process.

The beam-plate is divided into four subregions ($i=1,2,3,4$) with respect to the embedded delamination; perfect sublaminates ($i=1,4$), upper ($i=3$) and lower sublaminates ($i=2$). The deformation of each sublaminates can be represented by deflection w_i , axial displacement u_i , rotation ψ_i based on the first order shear deformation theory.

The total potential energy of the axially loaded i -th sublaminates consists of strain energy, U_i , and work, V_i , done by the external force.

$$U_i = \frac{1}{2} \iint \left(\frac{E_x}{1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}} \varepsilon_{ix}^2 + k G_{xy} \gamma_{ixy}^2 \right) dx dy \quad (1)$$

$$V_i = -P_i \left[\int (u_{i,x} + y \cdot \psi_{i,x}) dx + \frac{1}{2} \int w_{i,x}^2 dx \right] \quad (2)$$

The following expressions are substituted in Equation 1, 2 for the second variation.

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &\rightarrow u_i^o + u_i^a \\ \psi_i &\rightarrow \psi_i^o + \psi_i^a \\ w_i &\rightarrow w_i^o + w_i^a \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

(u^o, w^o, ψ^o) denote first equilibrium state and (u^a, w^a, ψ^a) denote admissible variations. The second variation is the sum of all terms that are quadratic in (u^a, w^a, ψ^a) . Thus the second variation of the total potential energy is given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta^2 \Pi &= \delta^2 U + \delta^2 V \\ &= \int F dx \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F &= -\frac{E_x h_i}{1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}} u_{i,x}^{a2} + D_i \psi_{i,x}^{a2} + k G_{xy} h_i (\psi_i^{a2} + 2 \psi_i^a w_{i,x}^a + w_{i,x}^{a2}) - P_i^o w_i^{a2} \\ P_i^o &= \frac{E_x h_i}{1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}} u_{i,x}^o \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

From the above equations and the Euler equations of the calculus of variations, governing Equation 5a, 5b, 5c of each sublaminates can be obtained as follows.

$$D_i \psi_{i,xx}^a - k G_{xy} h_i (\psi_i^a + w_{i,x}^a) = 0, \quad (5a)$$

$$k G_{xy} h_i (\psi_{i,x}^a + w_{i,xx}^a) - P_i^o w_{i,xx}^a = 0, \quad (5b)$$

$$u_{i,xx}^a = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, 4) \quad (5c)$$

where

$$h_1 = H, h_2 = H - h, h_3 = h, h_4 = H$$

2.2. Buckling Load

The solutions of Equation 5a, 5b, 5c are given as follows.

$$w_i^a = a_{i1} \cos \lambda_i x + a_{i2} \sin \lambda_i x + a_{i3} x + a_{i4}, \quad (6)$$

$$\psi_i^a = a_{i1} \lambda_i (1 - s \bar{p}_i) \sin \lambda_i x - a_{i2} \lambda_i (1 - s \bar{p}_i) \cos \lambda_i x - a_{i3} \quad (7)$$

$$u_i^a = k_{i1}x + k_{i2} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\lambda_1^2 = \frac{1}{1-s\bar{p}_1} \frac{P_1^0}{D_1}, \quad \lambda_2^2 = \frac{1}{1-s\bar{p}_2/(1-\bar{h})} \frac{P_2^0}{D_2}, \quad \lambda_3^2 = \frac{1}{1-s\bar{p}_3/\bar{h}} \frac{P_3^0}{D_3}, \quad \lambda_4^2 = \frac{1}{1-s\bar{p}_4} \frac{P_4^0}{D_4}, \quad (9)$$

$$s = \frac{4\pi^2 D_1}{kG_{xy}HL^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{3(1-\nu_{xz}\nu_{zx})} \frac{E_x}{kG_{xy}} \left(\frac{H}{L}\right)^2, \quad \bar{p}_i = \frac{P_i^0}{4\pi^2/L^2} \quad (10)$$

The deformations of each sublaminates can be represented by the above equations and have to satisfy four deflection continuity conditions, four rotation continuity conditions, four inplane displacement continuity conditions at both delamination fronts and six boundary conditions at both fixed ends. Six force equilibrium conditions (two axial forces, moments, and shear forces) must also be satisfied. Then, these 24 conditions with Equation 6, 7, 8 yield a linear system of equations. The system of linear algebraic equations are represented as follows.

$$[F]\{X\} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\{X\}^T = \{\bar{a}_{11}, \bar{a}_{12}, \bar{a}_{21}, \bar{a}_{22}, \bar{a}_{23}, \bar{a}_{31}, \bar{a}_{32}, \bar{a}_{33}, \bar{a}_{41}, k_{31}\} \quad (12)$$

where

$$\bar{a}_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{H}, \quad \bar{a}_{i3} = a_{i3} \frac{L}{H} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, 4, j = 1, 2, 4)$$

Consequently, buckling load can be expressed in terms of eigenvalue, $\lambda_1 L$, which makes the determinant of matrix $[F]$ vanished. Then, from Equation 9, buckling load \bar{P}_1 is given as Equation 13 in terms of $\lambda_1 L$.

$$\bar{P}_1 = \frac{(\lambda_1 L / 2\pi)^2}{1 + s \cdot (\lambda_1 L / 2\pi)^2} \quad (13)$$

2.3. Strain Energy Release Rate

2.3.1. Postbuckling state

For the calculation of the strain energy release rate, required are the deflections and the rotations at the delamination front in the postbuckling state. In this study, postbuckling analysis is limited to the symmetrical delamination located in the middle of the beam-plate as shown in Figure 2. The deflections and the rotations of each sublaminates can be expressed as follows by the symmetry conditions and boundary conditions.

$$w_2 = A \left\{ \frac{(1-s\bar{P}_4)}{[1-s\bar{P}_2/(1-\bar{h})]} \frac{\lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 b}{\lambda_2 \sin(\lambda_2 a / 2)} [\cos \lambda_2 x - \cos(\lambda_2 a / 2)] + 1 - \cos \lambda_4 b \right\}, \quad (14a)$$

$$0 \leq x \leq \frac{a}{2}$$

$$w_3 = A \left\{ \frac{(1-s\bar{P}_4)}{[1-s\bar{P}_3/\bar{h}]} \frac{\lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 b}{\lambda_3 \sin(\lambda_3 a / 2)} [\cos \lambda_3 x - \cos(\lambda_3 a / 2)] + 1 - \cos \lambda_4 b \right\}, \quad (14b)$$

$$0 \leq x \leq \frac{a}{2}$$

$$w_4 = A \left\{ 1 - \cos \lambda_4 \left(\frac{L}{2} - x \right) \right\}, \quad \frac{a}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (14c)$$

$$\psi_2 = (1-s\bar{P}_4) A \frac{\lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 b}{\sin(\lambda_2 a / 2)} \sin \lambda_2 x, \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{a}{2} \quad (15a)$$

$$\psi_3 = (1 - s\bar{P}_4)A \frac{\lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 b}{\sin(\lambda_3 a / 2)} \sin \lambda_3 x, \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{a}{2} \quad (15b)$$

$$\psi_4 = (1 - s\bar{P}_4)A \lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 \left(\frac{L}{2} - x \right), \quad \frac{a}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (15c)$$

The beam-plate must satisfy the axial-displacement compatibility, Equation 16a and the moment equilibrium condition, Equation 16b in the postbuckling state.

$$(1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}) \frac{P_3 a}{2E_x h} + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\frac{a}{2}} (w_{3,x})^2 dx \quad (16a)$$

$$= (1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}) \frac{P_2 a}{2E_x (H - h)} + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\frac{a}{2}} (w_{2,x})^2 dx - \frac{\psi_3(a/2)H}{2}$$

$$M_2^a + M_3^a - M_4^a + \frac{P_2^a h}{2} - \frac{P_3^a (H - h)}{2} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = \frac{a}{2} \quad (16b)$$

In order to get the following postbuckling state equations, Equations 14~15 are substituted in Equations 16a, 16b.

$$\left(\frac{A \lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 b}{2} \right)^2 \left\{ \left[\frac{1 - s\bar{P}_4}{1 - s\bar{P}_3 / h} \right]^2 \left[\frac{1}{\sin^2(\lambda_3 a / 2)} - \frac{1}{(\lambda_3 a / 2) \tan(\lambda_3 a / 2)} \right] \right.$$

$$\left. - \left[\frac{1 - s\bar{P}_4}{1 - s\bar{P}_2 / (1 - \bar{h})} \right]^2 \left[\frac{1}{\sin^2(\lambda_2 a / 2)} - \frac{1}{(\lambda_2 a / 2) \tan(\lambda_2 a / 2)} \right] \right\} \quad (17)$$

$$+ (1 - s\bar{P}_4) \frac{2H}{a} \left(\frac{A \lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 b}{2} \right) + \frac{1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}}{E_x} \left(\frac{P_3}{h} - \frac{P_4 - P_3}{H - h} \right) = 0$$

$$\left(\frac{A \lambda_4 \sin \lambda_4 b}{2} \right) (1 - s\bar{P}_4) \left[\bar{h}^3 \lambda_3 \cot \frac{\lambda_3 a}{2} + (1 - \bar{h})^3 \lambda_2 \cot \frac{\lambda_2 a}{2} + \lambda_4 \cot \lambda_4 b \right] \quad (18)$$

$$- \frac{3(1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx})}{E_x H^3} (HP_3 - hP_4) = 0$$

A and P_3 can be obtained when the axial load P_4 is given, since the above equations have only two unknowns A and P_3 . The deflections and the rotations are given through Equations 14~15, consequently axial force, moment, and shear force may be obtained by Equation 19.

$$V_i^a = kG_{xy} h_i (\psi_i^a + w_{i,x}^a) - P_i^o w_{i,x}^a, \quad M_i^a = D_i \psi_{i,x}^a \quad (19)$$

2.3.2. Formulation

The force equilibrium state at the delamination front consists of three equations-moment, axial force, shear force equilibrium equations. This equilibrium state can be divided into two subsystems, which satisfy force equilibrium as shown in Equations 20a~20c. First subsystem (M_i', P_i', V_i') is defined as follows;

$$M_i = M_i' + M_i'', \quad (20a)$$

$$P_i = P_i' + P_i'', \quad (20b)$$

$$V_i = V_i' + V_i'', \quad (20c)$$

$$M_1' = 0, \quad M_2' = M_2 - (1 - \bar{h})^3 M_1, \quad M_3' = M_3 - \bar{h}^3 M_1, \quad (21a)$$

$$P_1' = 0, P_2' = -P_3' = \bar{h} \left[P_1 + 6(1 - \bar{h}) \frac{M_1}{t} \right] - P_3, \quad (21b)$$

$$V_1' = 0, V_2' = -V_3' = V_3 - \bar{h}V_1 \quad (21c)$$

Second subsystem (M_i'' , P_i'' , V_i'') represents a non-singular stress field near the delamination front. Since this subsystem vanishes stress intensity factors of mode I and II, it does not affect the energy release rate. So, only the first subsystem needs to be considered in calculation.

The decomposed loading parameters P^* , M^* and V^* are defined by Equation 22 in the first subsystem, thus the force equilibrium state at the delamination front is represented in Figure 3.

$$M^* = M_3 - \bar{h}^3 M_1, P^* = \bar{h} \left[P_1 + 6(1 - \bar{h}) \frac{M_1}{t} \right] - P_3, V^* = V_3 - \bar{h}V_1 \quad (22)$$

The energy release rate is formulated through the J-integral along the path around the delamination front. J-integral is the function of stresses in upper and lower sublaminates based on the definition. The energy release rate is given by Equation 24 in terms of P^* , M^* and V^* .

$$dJ \equiv \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} dy - T_i u_{i,x} ds = \left(\frac{1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}}{2E_x} \sigma_x^2 - \frac{\tau_{xy}^2}{kG_{xy}} \right) ds \quad (i, j = x, y) \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma = J &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} dJ + \int_{\frac{(H-h)}{2}}^{\frac{(H-h)}{2}} dJ \\ &= \frac{1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}}{2E_x h} \left[P^{*2} + 12 \left(\frac{M^*}{h} \right)^2 \right] - \frac{6}{5} \frac{V^{*2}}{kG_{xy} h} \\ &+ \frac{1 - \nu_{xz} \nu_{zx}}{2E_x (H - h)} \left[P^{*2} + 12 \left(\frac{P^* t / 2 - M^*}{H - h} \right)^2 \right] - \frac{6}{5} \frac{V^{*2}}{kG_{xy} (H - h)} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Buckling Load

The variables are normalized as follows and some parameters are defined for a parametric study.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a} &= \frac{a}{L}, \quad \bar{b} = \frac{b}{L} = \frac{L - a - l_1}{L} = 1 - \bar{a} - \bar{l}_1, \\ \bar{x} &= \frac{x}{L}, \quad \bar{h} = \frac{h}{H}, \quad \alpha = \frac{\bar{a}}{\bar{h}}, \quad \bar{c} = \frac{x_{\text{center}}}{L} \end{aligned}$$

The parameter α means the relative slenderness of the delaminated surface and parameter \bar{c} represents the location of delamination. x_{center} is the length between $x = 0$ and the delamination center. Shear deformation factor s , defined by Equation 10, varies from 0.02 to 1.5 for various composite materials with the value of L/H around 10~50. Thus, shear deformation factor s is reasonably chosen as 0.0, 0.2, and 0.5.

First, the buckling load is shown in Figure 4. The buckling load gets smaller as \bar{h} decreases or \bar{a} increases, that is to say, α increases. The buckling load nearly becomes the same to that of a perfect beam-plate as α decreases. Then, the buckling load varies rapidly as α approaches to a specific value. It decreases rapidly when α is larger than 0.7 for $\bar{h} = 0.5$, and 1.0 for $\bar{h} = 0.2$.

The variation of the buckling load with respect to the delamination location is shown in Figure 5. The buckling load varies widely around $\bar{a} = 0.2 \sim 0.7$. When $\bar{a} = 0.2$, the lowest buckling load

appears at $\bar{c} = 0.25$ unlike other cases. Generally, buckling load increases as \bar{h} increases. But when \bar{c} is small in case of $\bar{a} = 0.2$, that is to say, the delamination locates closely to the end of the beam-plate, the buckling load decreases as \bar{h} increases (Fig. 6).

3.2. Energy Release Rate

For the determination of delamination growth after buckling, the energy release rate at the delamination front is required. When the energy release rate is higher than the fracture toughness of the material, the growth initiates. Then, as the delamination length becomes longer, the energy release rate changes with respect to the growth. If the changed energy release rate is keeping higher than the fracture toughness, delamination growth continues. But, if the changed energy release rate becomes lower than the fracture toughness, the delamination grows no more. To estimate the stability of delamination growth, the variation of energy release rate with delamination growth must be examined (Fig. 7). The energy release rate is normalized as shown in Equation 25.

$$\bar{\Gamma} = \frac{\Gamma}{D_1 H^2 / L^4} \quad (25)$$

The energy release rate also varies with α . Especially, in case of small α value, the energy release rate does not become higher so it cannot reach the fracture toughness. Consequently, when the delamination is thick and short, delamination growth does not occur and the ultimate axial load capacity is determined by the buckling load. The energy release rate with various shear deformation factor s is represented in Figure 8. According to the results, the shear deformation effect increases energy release rate. In other words, the energy release rate with shear deformation effect is larger than that without shear deformation effect at the same load level. Therefore, considering shear deformation effect, the delamination growth occurs at a lower load level than that without consideration of shear deformation.

Since the shear deformation effect lowers the buckling load and delamination growth load, the ultimate axial load capacity is overestimated when the shear deformation is not taken into account. Figure 8 illustrates that the shear deformation effect also becomes larger for short and thick delamination (α is small), and becomes small for long and slender delamination (α is large).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The buckling load of orthotropic laminated beam-plate with through-the-width delamination is calculated by the energy variational principle based on shear deformation theory, and the delamination growth analysis is performed through the evaluation of the energy release rate.

1. The buckling load varies with the geometry of the delamination, especially geometric parameter α . The buckling load becomes the same as that of perfect beam-plate when the delamination becomes short and thick. The buckling load decreases as the delamination gets long and slender.
2. The buckling load varies with the delamination location. For the most part, the closer the delamination locates to one end, the lower the buckling load becomes.
3. Shear deformation effect lowers the buckling load and increases the energy release rate. The effect becomes larger in the short and thick delamination.

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Figure 1. Geometry of the model.

Figure 2. Geometry of the model for the postbuckling solution.

Figure 3. Decomposed loading parameter.

Figure 4. Effect of transverse shear deformation & delamination configuration on buckling load.

Figure 5. Effect of delamination location on buckling loads ($\bar{h} = 0.5$).

Figure 6. Buckling load for relatively short and thick delamination with various location ($\bar{\alpha} = 0.2$).

Figure 7. Energy release rate vs. axial load with various delamination length ($\bar{h} = 0.1, s = 0.2$).

Figure 8. Effect of transverse shear deformation on energy release rate.